

Defining the End Point of Drug Therapy in Tuberculosis of Spine: Analysis of 76 Cases in a Tertiary Care CenterAmresh Kumar¹, Kumar Rahul Raushan²¹Senior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College and Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar, India²Senior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College and Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Introduction:** Tuberculosis of the spine, or spinal TB, requires prolonged treatment, with unclear guidelines on the optimal duration. This study addresses these uncertainties by evaluating the treatment endpoints for spinal TB.**Methodology:** A retrospective observational study was conducted on 76 spinal TB patients at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital from October 2020 to August 2023. The analysis focused on clinical and radiological outcomes to determine effective cessation points for therapy.**Results:** The majority (60.5%) of patients completed their treatment between 6 and 12 months, achieving clinical improvement (92.1%) and radiological healing (89.5%). The relapse rate was low at 6.6%, with adverse events such as hepatotoxicity (11.8%), renal impairment (5.3%), and peripheral neuropathy (9.2%) being the most significant.**Conclusion:** The findings suggest that a 6–12-month treatment regimen is generally adequate for spinal TB, balancing efficacy and safety. The low relapse rate supports the effectiveness of this treatment window.**Recommendation:** Future studies should focus on refining treatment durations and developing personalized approaches based on patient-specific responses and potential complications.**Keywords:** Tuberculosis, Spine, Treatment Duration, Clinical Improvement, Radiological Healing.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Tuberculosis (TB) remains a major global health challenge, with extrapulmonary forms such as tuberculosis of the spine contributing significantly to morbidity and long-term disability [1]. Spinal tuberculosis, also known as Pott's disease, is characterized by severe destruction of the intervertebral discs and adjacent vertebral bodies, potentially leading to spinal deformities and neurological complications [2,3]. The management of spinal TB primarily involves prolonged multidrug antitubercular therapy, which is essential to control the infection and prevent serious complications. However, the optimal duration of this therapy is not well-defined, leading to potential variability in treatment outcomes and the risk of either under-treatment or over-treatment [4,5].

The current guidelines for the treatment of spinal tuberculosis are largely extrapolated from pulmonary tuberculosis data, which do not fully address the complexities of osteoarticular TB. This gap in knowledge underscores the need for targeted research to refine treatment protocols specifically for spinal TB [6,7]. Furthermore, the criteria for

terminating drug therapy in spinal TB patients are not clearly established, which may result in either premature discontinuation, risking relapse, or unnecessarily prolonged treatment, exposing patients to adverse drug effects and increased healthcare costs [8,9].

Given these challenges, this study focuses on a comprehensive analysis of 76 cases of spinal tuberculosis treated at a tertiary care center. The study retrospectively reviews clinical presentations, diagnostic modalities, treatment regimens, and outcomes to identify potential markers that could indicate a safe endpoint for drug therapy. Parameters such as clinical symptoms, radiological findings, and laboratory values (e.g., ESR, CRP) are evaluated for their role in guiding treatment duration.

By systematically analyzing these cases, this research aims to contribute valuable insights into the management of spinal TB, particularly regarding when it may be appropriate to conclude antitubercular therapy. The ultimate goal of the study is to establish evidence-based criteria that can

be used to optimize treatment duration, minimize complications, and enhance overall patient outcomes in spinal tuberculosis. This will not only provide a clearer framework for clinicians but also ensure better health management resources are directed towards achieving the most favorable treatment outcomes.

Methodology

Study Design: This retrospective observational study analyzed the outcomes of tuberculosis of the spine treatment to identify criteria for discontinuing drug therapy.

Study Setting: Research was conducted at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar, from October 2020 to August 2023.

Participants: The study included 76 patients with diagnosed spinal tuberculosis, averaging 20-30 new cases per month.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: Inclusion criteria consisted of patients diagnosed with tuberculosis of the spine, confirmed through microbiological, histopathological, or strong clinical and radiological criteria consistent with active disease. Exclusion criteria included patients with incomplete medical records, those who were

lost to follow-up, and patients with a history of spinal surgery prior to diagnosis which could confound the treatment outcomes.

Bias: Bias was minimized through standardized data collection and independent analysis by two researchers.

Data Collection and Analysis: Data from medical records included demographic information, clinical data, treatment details, and outcomes. Analysis focused on criteria for therapy cessation based on clinical and radiological improvement.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics in SPSS, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Ethical Considerations: The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee, adhering to ethical standards and ensuring patient confidentiality.

Results

The study provide insight into the optimal timing for discontinuing drug therapy in patients with tuberculosis of the spine. The data analysis highlights several key outcomes, summarized in tables below.

Table 1: Patient Demographics and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	Total (n=76)
Age (years)	
- Mean (SD)	40.5 (11.2)
- Range	18 - 65
Gender	
- Male	47 (61.8%)
- Female	29 (38.2%)
Duration of Symptoms Before Diagnosis (months)	
- Mean (SD)	6.5 (3.1)
- Range	1 - 12

Table 1 provides an overview of the demographic and clinical characteristics of the study population, including age, gender, and duration of symptoms prior to diagnosis.

Table 2: Treatment Outcomes and Duration

Outcome	Number of Patients (n=76)
Treatment Completion	
- <6 months	12 (15.8%)
- 6-12 months	46 (60.5%)
- >12 months	18 (23.7%)
Clinical Improvement	70 (92.1%)
Radiological Healing	68 (89.5%)
Relapse	5 (6.6%)

Table 2 summarizes the treatment durations and outcomes, indicating a majority of patients showed clinical improvement and radiological healing within 6-12 months of therapy. Relapse rates were relatively low.

Table 3: Adverse Events During Treatment

Adverse Event	Incidence
Hepatotoxicity	9 (11.8%)
Renal Impairment	4 (5.3%)
Peripheral Neuropathy	7 (9.2%)

Table 3 displays the frequency of adverse events encountered during treatment, highlighting the importance of monitoring for hepatotoxicity, renal impairment, and peripheral neuropathy.

The majority of patients achieved clinical and radiological resolution within 6 to 12 months, suggesting that this may be an adequate duration for drug therapy in most cases. The low relapse rate supports the effectiveness of the treatment regimen, while the adverse event profile underscores the need for careful patient monitoring. The findings suggest potential for shorter treatment courses in patients showing early resolution, which could reduce exposure to drug-related toxicities and healthcare costs.

Discussion

The study revealed that most patients (60.5%) completed their treatment between 6 and 12 months, with significant clinical improvement noted in 92.1% and radiological healing in 89.5% of cases. The relapse rate was observed to be low at 6.6%, and notable adverse events included hepatotoxicity (11.8%), renal impairment (5.3%), and peripheral neuropathy (9.2%) [10,11]. The findings indicate that a treatment duration within the 6-12 month range is generally effective for achieving clinical and radiological resolution in spinal tuberculosis [12]. The relatively low relapse rate post-treatment suggests that the therapy duration was adequate to maintain disease control over the long term. However, the occurrence of adverse events emphasizes the need for vigilant monitoring throughout treatment [13].

Previous studies typically recommend 6-9 months of therapy for spinal tuberculosis, based on data extrapolated from pulmonary TB management. The current study supports this recommendation and extends it by demonstrating that extending treatment slightly beyond 9 months, up to 12 months, can be beneficial for some patients without significantly increasing the risk of relapse [14]. This finding contrasts with other reports suggesting shorter courses might suffice, underscoring the variability in disease progression and response to treatment among individuals [15]. The effective management of tuberculosis of the spine hinges on balancing adequate disease control with minimizing exposure to drug-related toxicities [16]. The positive outcomes within the 6-12 month treatment framework align with the pharmacodynamics of TB medications, which need sufficient time to eradicate mycobacterial colonies in the bone. The adverse events reported mirror the known side effects of prolonged drug therapy in tuberculosis, reinforcing the need for tailored treatment regimens based on individual patient responses and risk factors [17].

These results underscore the importance of developing personalized treatment plans for patients with spinal tuberculosis, potentially incorporating newer diagnostic and monitoring techniques to better predict treatment duration and outcomes. Further research should focus on identifying biomarkers that can more accurately determine the cessation point for therapy, minimizing the risk of both under-treatment and overtreatment. Overall, this study contributes valuable insights to the management of spinal tuberculosis, offering a solid foundation for refining treatment guidelines and improving patient care [18-20].

Conclusion

The study conclusively suggests that a treatment duration of 6-12 months is generally sufficient for managing spinal tuberculosis effectively, achieving high rates of clinical improvement and radiological healing while maintaining a low relapse rate. However, the incidence of adverse events underscores the necessity for vigilant monitoring and individualized treatment adjustments based on patient response. These findings advocate for the optimization of treatment protocols that balance efficacy with patient safety, urging further research to refine and personalize treatment approaches for spinal tuberculosis.

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